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**Biodistance studies in the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East:
An overview and future prospects**

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Abstract

Biodistance studies have a long presence in Eastern Mediterranean and Middle Eastern (EMME) bioarchaeology. In line with trends seen in North America and elsewhere, such studies were originally typological and were often adopted to explore mass migrations, while after the advent of New Archaeology in the 1960s, the research questions started covering issues of past population structure and short-distance mobility, and the statistical methods adopted became increasingly sophisticated. Nowadays, despite the revolution in ancient DNA and isotope studies, biodistance analyses are still broadly applied in EMME assemblages to address an ever-expanding range of topics. This paper provides a brief overview of biodistance studies in this region, with an emphasis on their temporal evolution. In addition, it discusses the directions in which such studies should move in the near future, with an emphasis on the need for even more studies, association of the results with other bioarchaeological, material cultural, historical and ecological information, and methodological standardization.

Keywords: biological distance, gene flow, kinship patterns, population structure, Eastern Mediterranean, Middle East

1. Introduction

Biological distance or biodistance analysis uses skeletal phenotypic data to explore the relatedness of past populations, which may result from gene flow, common ancestry, or other processes (Buikstra et al., 1990; Hefner et al., 2016; Pietrusewsky, 2013). In biodistance studies the phenotype is used as a proxy for the genotype with the underlying assumption that skeletal phenotypic variation conveys phylogenetic information (Relethford, 2016). The skeletal phenotypic data examined include metric variables, mostly cranial and dental measurements, as well as nonmetric traits, that is, morphological variants the expression of which cannot be measured in a linear manner (see contributions in Pilloud and Hefner, 2016).

The present paper aims at providing an overview of biodistance studies in the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East (hereafter EMME) to demonstrate trends in relevant research in this region and highlight the current state of knowledge, elucidating existing gaps and the need for targeted research to address them. Before proceeding, a limitation of this review must be highlighted: This paper could only present some of the biodistance studies conducted in the EMME region, while others have been omitted either due to word limit restrictions or because they could not be accessed. Nonetheless, research results from over 55 studies published in physical anthropology and osteoarchaeology journals, edited volumes, as well as graduate dissertations are briefly presented, providing an overview of the work that has been carried out by scholars in different contexts and at different stages in their career.

2. A brief history of biodistance studies

Biodistance studies have a long presence within the discipline of anthropology as cranial anatomy held a central place in the “race science” of the late 18th century (Blumenbach, 1775). Most early craniometric studies were typological, aiming at classifying individuals into morphologically similar groups (races) (e.g. Blumenbach, 1775; Broca, 1863; Hrdlička, 1927; Morton, 1839). This trend was also linked to an emphasis of biodistance analysis to study “ancient migrations”, which also had a strong typological descriptive focus (see review by Stojanowski, 2019, and summary of relevant research by Wolfram, 1993). With the advent of New Archaeology at the end of the 1960s, new research questions emerged. Biological distance analysis started addressing issues of past population structure and short-distance mobility (e.g. post-marital residence practices) rather than mass migrations and typological racial divisions (Buikstra, 1979; Corruccini, 1972; Lane and Sublett, 1972; Rightmire, 1970; Van Gerven et al., 1973).

The abovementioned developments were accompanied by important methodological advances with regard to the statistical methods available for the study of phenotypic data (see concise review in Hefner et al., 2016). Early 20th century biodistance studies adopted the so-called “coefficient of racial likeness” (Pearson, 1926), which quantified the degree of similarity between two populations using skeletal metric data. Among the key limitations of this coefficient was the fact that it could not account for intercorrelated measurements/variables, and it was affected by the number of variables in the dataset (Seltzer, 1937). Alternative measures were proposed by Fisher (1936) and Mahalanobis (1936) for comparing two populations and estimating group distances, respectively, while a few years later, Penrose (1952) proposed a statistic to compare distances in mean measurements between populations, taking into account “shape” and “size”. So far, biodistance statistics had focussed on metric data. In 1953 Sanghvi proposed a distance statistic for nonmetric traits (frequency data)

(Sanghvi, 1953). The 1970s was marked by the introduction of the Mean Measure of Divergence (Smith, 1972), a measure that utilises the differences in trait frequency among groups, taking into account the variance found within each group. This decade also witnessed an emphasis on population genetics (Harpending and Jenkins, 1973); nonetheless, it took several more years for relevant approaches to be extended to quantitative traits (Relethford and Blangero, 1990).

In the 21st century, biodistance studies are still popular, as attested by a substantial number of scientific publications and graduate theses on the subject (see Pilloud and Hefner, 2016 for forensic and bioarchaeological perspectives of biodistance analysis, covering a review of the field, methodological issues and case studies). It is notable that this trend is observed despite the rapid development of ancient DNA (aDNA) and stable isotope studies regarding past mobility, which one would anticipate to have marginalised biodistance analysis. Among the factors that have been linked to the popularity of biodistance studies is the non-destructive nature of data collection, which allows for including the entire available skeletal assemblage in the analysis, the generalization of the use of geometric morphometrics instead of traditional linear measurements (McKeown, 2000), the low cost of application, as well as the fact that, as macroscopic methods, they can be adopted irrespective of the degree of diagenesis and contamination that the skeletal and dental tissues have undergone, which pose serious limitations in the applicability of chemical and biomolecular analyses. Nowadays, a wide range of statistical methods are available for biodistance studies, both for metric and nonmetric data, which further promotes the use of relevant approaches. As an example, a recent PhD dissertation (Adams, 2020) employed the Mean Measure of Divergence, Mahalanobis distance and coefficients of variation for inter-site comparisons, and Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn's Tests, Fuzzy c-means, Gower's Coefficient of Similarity, Covariance Matrix Determinant Ratio, Mean Pairwise Differences, Shannon's Diversity Index, Simpson's Diversity Index, Pielou's Evenness Measure, and Hill Numbers for intra-site analyses. The implementation of relevant measures is also now greatly facilitated by open access software (e.g. Santos, 2018; Sołtysiak, 2011; several R packages such as *HDMD*, *cluster*, *dunn.test*, *ppclust*, *Statmatch*, *vegan*).

3. Biodistance studies in the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East

With the EMME witnessing networks of exchange since the Palaeolithic, it is not surprising that biodistance studies appeared in this area as early as the late 18th century (Busk, 1875). The map of Figure 1 shows the location of the EMME sites included in biodistance studies presented in this review. It can be seen that such studies have been numerous and cover a large part of the region. The evolution of the themes and research questions addressed by biodistance studies has largely followed the trends seen in the rest of the world. Following Konigsberg (2006), these themes broadly fall under: 1. indigenous development vs. migration, 2. local migration, and 3. temporal variation.

3.1. Early 19th c. to 1960s

Studies from the early 19th century had a strong typological character, aimed at describing the characteristics of different past populations in the region and divide these into races (e.g. Petrie, 1901). From the 1930s biodistance studies focussed at identifying large-scale

migration events to ascertain the origin of past populations. By the 1960s studies had become increasingly hypothesis-driven, yet they remained overall strongly typological in nature.

A typical example of biodistance research during this early period is the study by Risdon (1939), which examined the origin of the Lachish people through craniometric comparisons with ancient Egyptians. At the same time, there are papers that offer a general morphological and metric description of skeletal remains and broad comparisons with other groups without a clear research question. An example in this category is Dahlberg's (1960) paper on the Jarmo dentition. The author provides a description of the dental metric and morphological characteristics of the early agriculturalists of Jarmo (Iraq) and finds that they have many similarities to those of modern Mediterranean and European groups, while they exhibit no traits commonly found in Asian populations.

Lawrence Angel's work in the eastern Mediterranean is notable for the study of diverse aspects of past skeletal biology, not least for his biodistance studies. Angel (1944, p. 330) examined the "racial changes which accompany historical developments" in ancient Greece. Using craniometrics and employing material from multiple archaeological sites across Greece that date from Neolithic to Byzantine times, Angel concluded that ancient Greeks are particularly heterogeneous and fall into six morphological types: "Basic White", "Classic Mediterranean", "Nordic-Iranian", "Dinaric-Mediterranean", "Mixed Alpine", and "Alpine". In addition, the author identified two sources of gene flow: one from the southeast and one from the north. Even though this early paper aims at outlining "the racial history of Greece" (Angel, 1944, p. 329), the author also sets out to explore the "validity of morphological types" (Angel, 1944, p. 329) and interprets the findings in light of historical events and evolutionary processes, such as environmental adaptation and gene flow. A year later, Angel (1945) set out to explore the origin of ancient Greeks. Using cranial measurements from Neolithic sites across Greece, he found striking "racial heterogeneity" (Angel, 1945, p. 260) characteristic of the skeletal material, which matches the cultural divergence between Greek Neolithic sites. However, he also cautions that the sample size is particularly small and only allows very tentative conclusions.

Another rather early study that stands out is by Berry et al. (1967) on diachronic genetic change in ancient Egyptians. The authors examined cranial nonmetric traits on skeletal assemblages across Egypt, spanning almost 5,000 years. The results suggested a high degree of homogeneity in the Egyptian population during this broad time period and were interpreted as a lack of "great racial intermingling" (Berry et al., 1967, p. 566). The authors proposed three interpretations for their findings: 1. the techniques used were not sensitive enough to identify gene flow; 2. the incomers were few and became absorbed to the local gene pool, not affecting the genotype of future generations; 3. the incomers did not differ genetically from the local Egyptian groups. Even though this study is still looking for large-scale gene flow, in line with most early biodistance studies, it frames the research question within the context of gene flow and population structure and avoids over-simplistic interpretations.

3.2. 1970s and 1990s

The number of biodistance studies in the EMME region increased notably from the 1970s onwards and the research questions started shifting away from typological approaches and the

search for large migration episodes. Instead, studies now aimed at exploring whether changes observed in the material culture in different regions were the result of local/indigenous developments that occurred without any particular external stimuli or due to the arrival of new human groups in the region (e.g., Arensburg and Belfer-Cohen, 1992; Rathburn, 1982). Therefore, there is still a link with past migration studies but at the same time an acknowledgement that indigenous processes are equally -if not more- important in generating change. In addition, biodistance studies started examining local, short-distance, migration (or its lack) in the form of endogamy and patrilocal or matrilineal post-marital residence patterns (e.g., Johnson and Lovell, 1994; Prowse and Lovell, 1996). Finally, a number of studies examined the degree and expression of diachronic biological variation in archaeological assemblages. These studies were often associated to the ones exploring indigenous developments versus migration-related change by showing a broader time span (e.g., Arensburg and Rak, 1985; Finkel, 1978; Keita, 1990). Note that this shift in research questions at this period is aligned with patterns seen in biodistance studies beyond the EMME (e.g. Konigsberg, 2006).

Rathburn's (1982) work is a typical example of the aforementioned developments in biodistance studies. The author obtained cranial measurements from multiple Middle Eastern sites dating to the Copper, Bronze and Iron Age (3200-200 BC) to test whether migration may explain archaeologically-attested sociocultural developments or not. The results did not identify any large-scale gene flow. Interestingly, females were found to be more mobile than males, which the author linked to practices of patrilineality and patrilocality or to female dislocation due to warfare, trade, political alliances, or other causative factors.

Another study that explored the biodistance of Middle Eastern populations, this time from 3200 BC to 300 AD, was by Finkel (1978). The author examined diachronic spatial and temporal relationships of South European and Middle Eastern populations through craniometric data. In agreement with Rathburn's (1982) study, the results revealed few significant differences, which the author interpreted as the result of natural selection rather than migration and genetic drift.

On a more regional scale, McGeorge's (1983) PhD thesis explored the affinities of ancient Minoan populations across Crete dating to the 3rd and 2nd millennia BC, adopting craniometrics, as well as cranial, dental and postcranial nonmetric traits. The author found a close affinity of the Minoans with mainland Greeks, supporting other archaeological evidence of a strong contact network between Cretan and Peloponnesian populations. The Minoan populations also showed similarity to Early Neolithic populations of Cyprus, which was interpreted as suggestive of a common ancestry for these groups.

A study that explored the affinities of a single prehistoric population was by Macchiarelli (1989). The author used dental nonmetric traits to examine the affinities of the Ra's al-Hamra Mesolithic fishermen from Oman through comparisons with other Mesolithic and Neolithic EMME groups. The Ra's al-Hamra group was isolated on the Qurum promontory in Oman and the results of the biodistance analysis supported prolonged genetic isolation and inbreeding for this group as great differences were noted in dental morphology in comparison to eastern African and Middle Eastern populations.

Regional migration coupled with diachronic variation was the subject of work by Arensburg and Rak (1985), who examined the skeletal remains from a Jewish cemetery on the western

slopes of Mount Zion dating to the 7th c. BC as a case study. The authors compared the cranial measurements of this group with crania from other sites and periods in Israel and found the skulls from Mount Zion not to be substantially differentiated from the comparative assemblages. However, the authors identified increased heterogeneity among Israeli assemblages during the late Hellenistic to Byzantine period, which they attributed to the migration of Jewish populations after the destruction of Jerusalem by the Babylonians in 587 BCE.

Along the line of examining migration versus indigenous developments, Arensburg and Belfer-Cohen (1992) explored the affinities of the Tell 'Eitun skulls to test whether the "Philistine" grave goods associated with these skulls reflect the ethnic affiliation of the deceased. In particular, during the Iron Age two groups, Philistines and Israelites, arrived in the region. The extent to which the local inhabitants, Canaanites, mixed with the newcomers or remained isolated is unclear. Craniometric analysis showed that the Tell 'Eitun skulls were rather homogeneous and similar to later Iron Age remains, while the Iron Age population of Israel appeared similar to that of recent Bedouins, supporting a biological relationship to Mediterranean people. Hence, the material culture remains in the 'Eitun tomb did not reflect ethnic affiliation. Note however, that the above conclusions were based on merely seven individuals from Tell 'Eitun, and the authors do not specify what kind of statistical analysis they used to compare their morphology against comparative groups.

The correlation between material cultural networks and biological affinities was also tested by Blau (1998) in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). Combining the study of cranial shape, dental metrics and dental nonmetrics, and examining multiple sites across UAE dating from the 5th millennium BC to 100 AD, the author tested whether the maritime relationship between the ancient UAE and Mesopotamia in the 3rd millennium BC was characterised by extensive human gene flow or whether the circulation of material goods was via selected intermediaries. The author found that the majority of the skeletons under study exhibited "Caucasian" features, although there was some gene flow with groups outside the Gulf.

Issues on the origin of past populations still remained active, as attested for example by Smith (1982), who tested whether the Middle Bronze Age population of the Jebel Qa'aqir can be identified as the "Amorites," a Western Semitic group mentioned in the Ur III texts. The results suggested that the Jebel Qa'aqir population is related to earlier populations in the region; however, they belong to a Mediterranean type found throughout Syria, Israel, Jordan, and Iraq at the time, and the sample size was too small to permit a finer resolution of biological affinities.

Brace et al. (1993) also aimed at exploring the origin of past groups, namely that of ancient Egyptians. The authors additionally examined the extent to which Egyptian population structure has been affected by invasions and migrations. In this direction, the authors focussed on the biological affinities of the Late Dynastic Giza and Predynastic Naqada, and their craniometrics were compared to those of neighbouring groups and other prehistoric assemblages as well as against "samples representing the major geographic population clusters of the world" (Brace et al., 1993, p. 1). The results suggested that the Egyptians have been present in this area since the Pleistocene and they have been largely unaffected by the influx of other groups.

In a similar direction of exploring large-scale mobility in North Africa, Keita (1990) used cranial measurements from multiple North African sites, including a number of Egyptian ones, to test the variation within the northwest and northeast sub-regions of North Africa, the affinities between these subregions, and the affinities with European and southern African groups. The material dated from the post-Neolithic to the mid-Holocene and the results suggested prominent variation but also a local craniometric pattern shared between the late dynastic north Egypt and coastal Maghreb, as well as affinity between southern predynastic Egyptian groups and tropical Africa. These patterns have been attributed to microevolution and migration. In another study, Keita focussed specifically on the affinities of the elite from Abydos in Egypt (Keita, 1992). By means of craniometrics, he found greater affinity with Upper Nile Valley groups, but also a change from earlier craniometric trends, which he interpreted as suggestive of a possible influx of northern officials to the site of Abydos.

The affinities of elite Egyptian individuals were also the subject of study by Johnson and Lovell (1994) and Prowse and Lovell (1996), who tested the relationship among three predynastic Naqada cemeteries that represented people of different social status. The analysis of cranial and dental nonmetric traits suggested that individuals from the 'high status' cemetery were significantly differentiated from those buried in the non-elite cemeteries, while the non-elite individuals were not significantly different from each other. In addition, the high status cemetery was characterised by endogamy and was more closely related to Nubian than Egyptian populations.

Even at this rather mature stage in the evolution of biodistance studies, there are occasions where biodistance analysis has been employed without a clear research question but rather as part of the broader study of the metric and nonmetric variation of an assemblage. Such is the case for the Lambert (1980) study of the biological relationship between Ganj Dareh in modern-day Iran and other EMME prehistoric populations. Dental metrics were used as part of the study of general metric and nonmetric variation of the Neolithic population from this site compared to other EMME samples and suggested no relationship between Ganj Dareh and any of the other assemblages examined.

It is interesting to note that, as seen by the brief overview of studies above, the results of most biodistance studies during this period were against large-scale migrations, a trend also seen in other parts of the world (Konigsberg, 2006). In part, this phenomenon can be linked to the advent of New Archaeology and its rejection of migration theories that strongly characterized the earlier culture-historical phase of archaeological thought (Adams et al., 1978). Of course, one cannot claim that all biodistance studies at the time reached wrong conclusions with regard to migration versus indigenous change, but as Konigsberg (2006) notes in a North American bioarchaeological context, relevant studies had not yet established any particular methodology for using biodistance data to answer questions regarding migration, and the studies were often unclear on whether they had indeed proven the biological continuity of local groups. The same is largely true for EMME-focussed biodistance studies at the time.

3.3. 2000s onwards

During the past 20 years the interest in biodistance studies in the EMME has remained strong, with broader temporal and geographic coverage of larger- or smaller-scale gene flow.

Because of their large number, representative biodistance studies that took place in this region during the past 20 years will be presented in this section based on their geographic distribution. For simplicity, modern-day national borders will be used for the aforementioned geographic distribution; however, it is acknowledged that these borders had little to no meaning in the past in this region.

3.3.1. Libya

Biodistance studies in Libya have focussed on the Garamantes, a population that occupied the Sahara Desert (Fezzan region) from approximately 900 BC to 500 AD. A key research question has been the extent to which the material cultural networks in which this group had engaged were accompanied by large-scale human mobility. The analysis of cranial nonmetric traits and 3D geometric morphometrics of the cranial shape, supported that the Garamantes are phenotypically distant to other groups from Egypt, Algeria, Tunisia and Sudan, suggesting that the Sahara posed a barrier to extensive gene flow (Nikita et al., 2012a, 2012b). Similarly, the Garamantes were found to exhibit phenotypic continuity from the Late Pastoral to Roman times, but at the same time they engaged in some gene flow with other, likely sub-Saharan, groups (Ricci et al., 2013).

3.3.2. Egypt

The biodistances within Egypt as well as between Egypt and neighbouring regions have been the subject of numerous studies. Some of these studies explored the extent of diachronic continuity or change from the Neolithic to the Roman period and supported the former, using dental nonmetric traits (Irish, 2006). Other studies focussed on state formation in ancient Egypt and, again using dental nonmetric traits, found that this originated as an indigenous development with some contribution by immigrants (Schillaci et al., 2009). Similar results were obtained when adopting craniometric analysis, which showed population continuity from the Predynastic to the early Dynastic period, suggesting that state formation was an indigenous process but with some immigration having taken place in the Egyptian Nile Valley (Zakrzewski, 2007). Additionally to performing original data collection to explore intra-Egyptian biodistances, researchers have also estimated the biodistance of remains that are no longer available for study but only exist in documentation form. In specific, Keita and Godde (2016) used measurements published in Wiercinski (1978) to test archaeological theories of political unification under a single pharaoh from the Predynastic through Early Dynastic Egypt. Their findings, though based on small sample sizes, supported models of assimilation and interaction rather than population replacement of northern Egyptians by southern groups.

The topic of gene flow between Egypt and Nubia has attracted a lot of attention and it has been examined by means of craniometrics (Buzon, 2008) and cranial nonmetric traits (Godde, 2009, 2018). These studies have identified gene flow between Nubian and Egyptian populations, as supported also by networks of material culture (Buzon, 2008; Godde, 2009). More recent works have refined the research questions to explore how far back in time the similarity of these groups dates and proposed that relevant population events predate the Mesolithic period (Godde, 2018).

The biological affinity of specific Egyptian groups to other Egyptian (and Nubian) assemblages has also been explored to assess their origin and relationship. In this direction, based on dental nonmetric traits, Hierakonpolis exhibited a closer association with Nubians than Egyptians (Irish, 2007; Irish and Friedman, 2010), while the study of Gebel Ramlah affinities with Egyptian, Nubian, Mediterranean and sub Saharan African groups, suggested multiple places of origin, admixture, and possible descendants in Upper Egypt and Nubia (Irish, 2010).

A final topic explored in Egyptian biodistance studies is intra-cemetery kinship patterns. Such patterns have been examined at the Kellis 2 cemetery based on dental and vertebral nonmetric traits (Haddow, 2012; Sarfo, 2014). Both studies identified some extent of kin-structured patterning of the tombs. Similar patterns were found at the Amarna South Tombs cemetery, which appeared to have been organised by biological kinship, as deduced from dental measurements, a trend particularly visible for the female part of the population (Schaffer, 2018).

3.3.3. Greece

Recent biodistance studies in Greece have explored issues of gene flow versus material cultural networks, population history and kinship patterns. An example of the former explored the relationship among Early and Middle Minoan assemblages and the extent to which gene flow matches the archaeologically attested networks of contact within the island. The results of the biodistance study identified a complex network of human mobility and interaction on the island of Crete, supporting that material networks of contact were often accompanied by gene flow, but this was not always the case (Nikita et al., 2017; Triantaphyllou et al., 2015).

With regard to population history, diachronic continuity or discontinuity of the population in Akraiphia, central Greece, was examined, as well as the possible influx of groups linked to important historical events from the Archaic to the Late Roman times. The analysis of dental nonmetric traits revealed a separation of the Archaic, Classical and Hellenistic period material from the Roman and Late Roman material. This pattern suggested population history continuity until the Hellenistic period, and an event that differentiated the local gene pool occurring between the Hellenistic period and the Roman era. This event may be linked to Augustus' *Pax Romana*, which facilitated free movement and resulted in high rates of population turnover in different Roman sites (Nikita et al., 2019).

Finally, kinship patterns and postmarital residence were explored at the cemetery at Tsepi Marathon in Attica for the Final Neolithic and early Bronze Age period. The combined analysis of dental metrics, dental nonmetrics, and cranial nonmetrics, suggested that within-tomb burial depended on multiple factors that could include different types of kinship. Very interestingly, strong evidence for phenotypic patterning by tomb row was identified, indicating that the Tsepi cemetery was organised according to biological lineages. This was especially evident for females, likely supporting matrilocality (Prevedorou and Stojanowski, 2017).

3.3.4. Turkey

A number of studies have explored aspects of Anatolian population history. At a large geographical and temporal scale, migration episodes and complex patterns in the biological relations between Anatolian populations and populations that lived in different geographical areas between the Early Bronze Age to the early 20th century have been identified (Çırak et al., 2014; Eroğlu and Erdal, 2008). At a more regional scale, the comparison of the cranial shape of Byzantine Iznik, a heterogeneous assemblage consisting of Byzantines and Turks, with modern-day assemblages found no significant difference, suggesting population continuity in the region (Özdemir et al., 2010). Issues of intra-cemetery kinship patterns have also been examined for Neolithic Çatalhöyük (Pilloud and Larsen, 2011) and Early Bronze Age İkiztepe (Welton, 2010). The former study combined dental metric and nonmetric traits, and the latter used craniometrics. Both of them found a lack of biological kinship structure in the burial areas, which suggests that maybe an alternative definition of kin was in place that goes beyond biological factors. Finally, there are studies that have explored Anatolian biodistances at different levels of geographical resolution, from the intra-cemetery level to a broader Eastern Mediterranean context. Such a recent study employed dental metric and nonmetric traits at Early Bronze Age Karataş-Semayü; at an inter-cemetery level, the study found that southwestern Anatolian populations are descended from Neolithic Anatolian groups but gene flow increased over time, while at an intra-cemetery level, Karataş-Semayük showed little evidence of biologically patterned mortuary practices and likely a patrilocal residence system. The non-kinship-constrained mortuary practices and the incorporation of outsider females were interpreted as strategies that enhanced community bonding at a time characterised by increasing migration and cultural contact (Adams, 2020).

3.3.5. Cyprus

In Cyprus the focus of biodistance studies has largely been on prehistoric material, exploring diachronic continuity and contact among Cypriot sites, as well as between Cyprus, mainland Greece and Syria by means of dental nonmetric traits (Parras, 2004). In the same direction, questions regarding how biological and cultural regionalism are reflected across time and space have also been posed. Relevant studies revealed heterogeneous biological affinities, which contradict the homogenous material culture of the later Neolithic and Chalcolithic periods, and the idea that biological regionalism resulted from the initial colonisation of the island of Cyprus was introduced (Parras, 2014). Even though the sample sizes on which the above studies were based are very small, thus only tentative conclusions can be drawn, the attempted link with archaeological/cultural evidence of gene flow and intra-island interaction of communities is notable.

3.3.6. Israel

Biodistance studies in Israel have addressed a range of topics, including intra-cemetery kinship patterns, ancestry and population continuity issues, as well as migration versus indigenous change. Familial relationships manifesting in the Pre-Pottery Neolithic B cemetery of Kfar HaHoresh were explored using dental nonmetric traits to see how social identities are expressed in a funerary context during the transition from hunting-gathering to

farming (Alt et al., 2015). The results revealed biological relatedness among some of the analysed individuals, especially among females and sub-adults, suggesting possible matrilocality. With regard to the theme of ancestry, a craniometric morphological resemblance between Chalcolithic groups from Peqi'in and Wadi Makkok and Bedouins, supported the ancient local roots of the latter (Nagar, 2011). Issues of population continuity were explored in the Negev Desert, where craniometric analyses revealed a continuity of the desert populations from the Hellenistic period until the modern era, as supported by the morphological resemblance of the Christian population of Byzantine Negev with earlier Nabataeans and later Bedouins (Nagar and Sonntag, 2008). Finally, the theme of migration versus indigenous development was addressed in the Late Bronze Age-Early Iron Age transition in the southern Levant and its link to the emergence of a new ethnicity (Ullinger et al., 2005). Dental nonmetric traits from the Late Bronze Age site of Dothan and the Iron Age site of Lachish were compared to dentitions from Byzantine Jerusalem, Iron Age Italy, a Natufian group, and a Middle Kingdom Egyptian site and the results supported that the similarity between Dothan and Lachish exceeds that of any of these assemblages and the comparative material. Therefore, the material culture changes that characterise the aforementioned transition were not the result of a foreign invasion.

3.3.7. Syria

In Syria biodistance studies have explored issues of kinship patterns and population history. With regard to the former, the study of familial patterns evidenced in Bronze Age Tell Umm el-Marra using dental nonmetric traits revealed some degree of genetic relatedness among the individuals buried within the same tomb (Batey, 2011); however, this conclusion was not based on any statistical analysis, but only on the relative frequency of a single nonmetric trait (Carabelli's trait). In what concerns population history, the extent of gene flow in the Middle Euphrates valley from the Early Bronze Age to modern times was the subject of study using dental nonmetric traits (Sołtysiak and Bialon, 2013). The results suggested an overall temporal homogeneity with the exception of modern times when differentiation of the local populations occurs. These findings led to the conclusion that gene flow across the Middle Euphrates valley between the 3rd millennium BCE and the early 2nd millennium CE was very limited, and agrees with other sources of information that support that population discontinuity in the region occurred only after the Mongolian invasion and depopulation of northern Mesopotamia in the 13th century CE and the subsequent repopulation of the region by Bedouin tribes from the Arabian Peninsula in the 17th century (Sołtysiak and Bialon, 2013).

3.3.8. Iraq

In modern-day Iraq, biodistance studies have been combined with mortuary data to explore the manifestation of the ethnic identity of ancient Akkadians, focussing on kinship patterns in a Kish cemetery. Employing cranial and dental nonmetric traits, some intra-cemetery biological differentiation was retrieved, which contrasts the relative homogeneity of the burial treatment. This finding was interpreted as suggestive of a lack of a distinct Akkadian ethnic identity or an attempt by those responsible for the funerary ritual to understate the

Sumerian-Akkadian ethnic differences (Pestle et al., 2014). Other biodistance studies in the region do not address any population history question but aim at creating a baseline for future research. In this direction, three-dimensional geometric morphometrics were used to examine temporal variations in craniofacial shape between populations from the Himrin Basin and neighbouring areas from the Chalcolithic to the Islamic period, and identified a change in craniofacial form between earlier and later assemblages but with limited attempt to interpret these findings (Ogihara et al., 2009).

3.3.9. Iran

Under the migration versus indigenous change theme, biodistance data were used to explore whether the transformations in material culture and mortuary practices, as well as the site abandonment and reoccupation that characterised the Central Iranian Plateau in the 5th to 2nd millennia BC are linked to the influx of new populations or not (Afshar, 2014). Using Tepe Hissar as a case study, the combination of cranial, dental and postcranial nonmetric traits, and cranial and dental measurements, suggested that the abovementioned changes were not accompanied by large scale population immigration. A study with a broader time span used craniometrics from skeletons from Ghal-e-Kash, Molla Kheil, Tepe Hissar and Shah Tepe to examine the biodistance of these groups, dating from the Chalcolithic to the Islamic period (Sołtysiak et al., 2009). The results supported a differentiation between early crania and crania dating to the Islamic period, as well as a clustering of the crania from Ghal-e-Kash and Molla Kheil with Islamic crania; however, the biodistance study was part of the broader osteological examination of the remains from Ghal-e-Kash and Molla Kheil, hence there is no discussion of the implications of the findings.

3.3.10. Bahrain

From 2250 BC to 1500 AD the area of modern-day Bahrain was characterised by prominent trade networks; however, it is unclear to what extent these networks are associated with large-scale human mobility. This issue was addressed by means of biodistance analysis employing craniometrics from multiple sites (Littleton, 2008). The results showed no dramatic change in cranial morphology in Bahrain over time, suggesting that trade did not create major gene flow. Interestingly, postcranial morphology was also studied to explore not just biodistance trends but also subsistence trends and how the two are associated. In this direction, the sexual dimorphism in postcranial morphology led to the conclusion that trade was more significant biologically in altering the living conditions than in promoting human mobility.

3.3.11. EMME assemblages within broader biodistance studies

In addition to the aforementioned studies that focussed primarily on EMME assemblages and research questions related to EMME archaeology, even if comparative material beyond this region was occasionally employed, a number of studies employed EMME material in broader population studies exploring the extent of demic diffusion during the Neolithic transition. Such an example is the study by Brace et al. (2006). By means of craniometrics, the authors

compared prehistoric and modern cranial morphologies across Europe and North Africa and found that prehistoric and modern peoples of Europe are not closely related. The authors interpreted this finding as suggesting that the Neolithic mode of economy entered Europe through demic diffusion but subsequently the local populations absorbed the incomers. In the same direction, von Cramon-Taubadel and Pinhasi (2011) obtained cranial metrics from Mesolithic and Neolithic assemblages and found that, whereas farming communities spread across Europe, hunter–gatherers in remote regions were not replaced but instead they adopted certain novel cultural elements, stressing the complexity of the transition to farming in Europe.

4. Future prospects of EMME biodistance studies

The above brief overview of biodistance studies in the EMME illustrates that this type of research has a long presence in the region and its evolution has largely followed the trends seen in other parts of the world, gradually shifting from typological approaches to research questions focussed on population history, and acknowledging the complexity of human mobility at different spatial and temporal scales.

Despite the substantial number of biodistance studies and their theoretical and methodological evolution, there are many issues that need to be addressed in the future. First of all, there is pressing need for an even greater number of biodistance studies in the region in order to achieve a more uniform geographic and temporal coverage. As can be seen from the map of Figure 1, at the moment certain countries and regions within these countries have been the focus of multiple biodistance studies, whereas others have largely been neglected. Even though the pattern seen in Figure 1 is biased by the fact that this paper only covered some of the biodistance studies in the region, it provides a good illustration of the spatial breadth of the majority of existing studies and the gaps that we should aim at covering. At this point, it should be highlighted that many of the archaeological sites included in biodistance studies had been based along the route of important material cultural networks (e.g. in Figure 1 it is seen that most of the sites examined so far were coastal or riverine, which would have increased their maritime connectivity) and they were largely the focus of biodistance studies in the context of research questions exploring the correspondence between material cultural networks and gene flow (e.g. Blau, 1998; McGeorge, 1983). It is important to move beyond this bias, and place more emphasis on assemblages and regions neglected to date in order to gain a better understanding of human mobility and population processes in the region diachronically. In this direction, as human mobility is a geographically and temporally continuous phenomenon, there is additional need for studies exploring large-scale spatial and temporal patterns in parallel with more regional/local mobility in order to disentangle this complex and dynamic process. In regions where this approach has been adopted to some extent, it has shown great potential and the need for more systematic study. For example, as outlined in section 3, McGeorge's (1983) PhD thesis stressed the affinity between Minoan populations, mainland Greeks and Cypriots; more recently, the work by Triantaphyllou et al. (2015) and Nikita et al. (2017) highlighted the complex pattern of human mobility and interaction within prehistoric Crete, which supports that when examining the affinities of prehistoric Minoans, it is important to take into account

regional heterogeneity within the island of Crete. The same principle undoubtedly applies to many different contexts.

Another important issue pertains to the use of other methods that may complement the results of biodistance analysis. Since biodistance studies are inherently linked with the study of human mobility, it is essential to combine such studies with the analysis of ancient DNA, oxygen and strontium isotopes as each of these methods may elucidate different aspects of past mobility. In biodistance studies the unit of the analysis is usually a group of individuals: whether all skeletons from a specific site compared to skeletons from other sites, or a small group of skeletons within a cemetery compared to other groups of skeletons from the same cemetery, depending on the research questions and spatial scale of the analysis (Pilloud and Hefner, 2016). Skeletons are individually assessed for phenotypic characters and then they are customarily put into statistics that evaluate them as groups (though there are exceptions where individual relationships and groupings are explored, e.g. Keita, 1990). In contrast, with ancient DNA and isotopic methods, the unit of the analysis is usually the individual. Depending on the research question, individual data may be pooled and treated as a group, but individual-specific analysis is very common, hence past mobility can be examined with greater resolution (e.g. Feldman et al., 2019; Mitchell and Millard, 2009). What is more, isotope microanalysis across incremental layers of the dental enamel may elucidate mobility patterns at different periods of an individual's lifetime (Maggiano et al., 2019). The complementary use of these methods may be part of the research design from the beginning or it may take place by different research groups, working decades apart. An example of the latter is the work by Gregoricka (2013), who performed strontium isotope analysis on largely the same assemblages that Blau (1998) had examined in the United Arab Emirates (UAE), aiming at addressing the same research question fifteen years later, namely whether the interregional exchange networks in the 3rd millennium BC were associated with extensive human gene flow. As mentioned in section 3, Blau (1998) found that most individuals exhibited "Caucasian" features, suggesting their local origin, although there was some gene flow with groups outside the Gulf. Gregoricka's (2013) strontium isotope results were in agreement to the earlier biodistance study as she found little isotopic variability between the individuals from different UAE sites, suggesting a population with limited mobility, while the author also identified three immigrants from Tell Abraq and Mowaihat, supporting some degree of gene flow with other regions. Another interesting example of the combined use of biodistance with stable isotope analysis is the work of Triantaphyllou et al. (2015). The biodistance results in this paper supported a distant affinity between the Kephala Petras assemblages and the Livari-Skiadi ones. Considering that Kephala Petras was a site strongly involved in material networks of exchange in the southern Aegean, one hypothesis was that there was strong gene flow between the inhabitants of this site and other neighbouring assemblages beyond Crete, which differentiated the local gene pool from that of other Cretan groups. However, strontium isotope analysis performed on a small sample of skeletons from Kephala Petras suggested that the individuals examined were of local origin, hence the observed distant affinities to other Cretan sites cannot be attributed to a prominent presence of immigrants at this site.

In the direction of combining biodistance data with other contextual information, it is important to engage in multidisciplinary research beyond bioarchaeology, that is, encompass textual sources, material culture, palaeoenvironmental data and other lines of evidence. Such

an approach has already been used in most biodistance studies, which frame the research questions based on information from written sources or material culture. For example, as presented in section 3, many biodistance studies examined whether material cultural networks were associated with gene flow or not (e.g. Nikita et al., 2017), while others have tested the origin of past groups and whether these match populations mentioned in ancient texts (Smith, 1982). Nonetheless, such an integration of diverse lines of evidence regarding past biodistances needs to become the norm and it should characterise the research questions but also any interpretation and discussion of the biodistance results. An example in this direction is The Hyksos Enigma project (<https://thehyksosenigma.oeaw.ac.at/>), which combines historiography, migration studies, material culture and bioarchaeology towards addressing various questions about ancient Hyksos, among which is the origin/ethnicity and the nature of immigration in the Hyksos dynasty.

Another important but rather neglected aspect is the need to combine biodistance studies with skeletal markers of stress, disease, demography, activity, diet and others pertaining to the daily life of past people in order to gain a better understanding of the differences in life quality between different clusters of individuals or locals and non-locals, as well as the impact that mobility had on the biology of the newcomers and the local groups. Whilst a number of studies in the EMME region have examined simultaneously many aspects of the osteobiography of past individuals, biodistances are largely viewed independently from skeletal markers of pathology, diet, activity etc. (e.g. Irish, 2010; Nikita et al., 2019) rather than within a single interpretive context.

Finally, there are a number of methodological issues pertaining to biodistance analyses that should be considered. The first of these relates to the multitude of available methods for collecting and analysing data, which may inhibit comparative studies. For example, even though recording dental nonmetric traits follows the standardised Arizona State University Dental Anthropology System (ASUDAS), the threshold adopted for presence-absence per trait may differ per researcher (e.g., see small differences in threshold values adopted by Irish 2006 and Turner 1987 in certain traits). Furthermore, different scholars adopt different nonmetric traits or measurements in their studies, which further limits cross-comparisons. An additional methodological issue pertains to the quantitative analysis of the collected data. Different data types (metric/nonmetric) require different statistical analyses, the results of which may not always be directly comparable. For example, nonmetric trait frequencies may be analysed using the Mean Measure of Divergence (Sjøvold, 1973) or pseudo-Mahalanobis distances (Konigsberg, 1990), while metric data are analysed primarily using Mahalanobis distances (Mahalanobis, 1936) or by estimating coefficients of variation (e.g., Carlson, 2017). On the other hand, the study of intra-cemetery kinship patterns adopts an entirely different set of quantitative analyses, such as binomial probabilities (Howell and Kintigh, 1996) and spatial data analysis (Ripley, 1976, 1977, 1981) for nonmetric traits, and various coefficients of similarity (e.g., Gower, 1971) for metric data. This variability in available quantitative methods has two important implications: 1. Different methods may not always produce the same results even when applied on the same datasets (Nikita, 2015), and 2. It may not be possible to compare the results of different studies, hence limiting the study of broader patterns. An additional issue in quantitative analysis is the small sample sizes that often characterise archaeological assemblages. Such samples raise the question of how representative they are of the original population under study and may lead to biased

statistical results. Finally, an important point that needs to be kept in mind is that biodistances are relative in the sense that they depend upon the groups included in the analysis. This means that the biodistance obtained between group A and group B will change depending upon the homogeneity or heterogeneity of the comparative materials included in the study.

Despite the aforementioned methodological limitations and the need for additional research and a greater integration of biodistance results with bioarchaeological, historical, material cultural and environmental data, biodistance studies have held an important place in EMME bioarchaeology. They have kept up with methodological and theoretical developments in North America and elsewhere, and they have been used to explore research topics central in EMME archaeology, pertaining to temporal variation, gene flow, and kinship. Seeing the evolution of such studies in the region, it is clear that the conditions have matured for the materialization of the abovementioned prospects and it is anticipated that biodistances will play an even more important role in the context of a broader biocultural study of the past inhabitants of the EMME.

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Figure

Figure 1. Sites examined in the biodistance studies presented in this review.

Key: 1. Garamantes, 2. Cairo, 3. Gizeh, 4. Lisht, 5. Tarkhan, 6. Saqqara, 7. Meidum, 8. Hawara, 9. Sedment, 10. Wadi Digla, 11. Maadi, 12. Helwan, 13. Amarna, 14. Manfalut, 15. Badari, 16. Qau el-Kebir, 17. Regagnah, 18. Dakhleh Oasis, 19. Kharga Oasis, 20. Abydos, 21. El Amrah, 22. Diospolis Parva, 23. Sheikh Ali, 24. Naqada, 25. Qurna, 26. Thebes, 27. Memphis, 28. Luxor, 29. Gebelein, 30. Hierakonpolis, 31. Hesa and Biga, 32. Gebel Ramlah, 33. Qustul, 34. Nea Nikomedeia, 35. Servia, 36. Olynthus, 37. Tsangli Magoula, 38. Choirospilia, 39. Astakos, 40. Akraiphia, 41. Tsepi Marathon, 42. Athens, 43. Nemea, 44. Ayioryitika, 45. Franchthi, 46. Maleme, 47. Nea Roumata, 48. Debla, 49. Chania, 50. Koumaro, 51. Platyvola, 52. Aptara, 53. Stylos, 54. Asfendou, 55. Fylaki, 56. Gerani, 57. Rethymno, 58. Armenoi, 59. Vrysinas, 60. Sybrita, 61. Ailias, 62. Gypsades, 63. Lato, 64. Tekes, 65. Monastiraki, 66. Apodhoulou, 67. Idaion Cave, 68. Kamares, 69. Phaistos, 70. Agios Onouphrios, 71. Agia Triada, 72. Kommos, 73. Moni Odigitria, 74. Lebena, 75. Koumasa, 76. Prinias, 77. Gortyn, 78. Tylissos, 79. Gazi, 80. Katsambas, 81. Fortetsa, 82. Knossos, 83. Juktas, 84. Archanes, 85. Vathypetro, 86. Amnissos, 87. Nirou Khani, 88. Pyrgos, 89. Mallia, 90. Kراسي, 91. Karphi, 92. Trapeza, 93. Kato Symi, 94. Myrtos, 95. Vrokastro, 96. Sphoungaras, 97. Gournia, 98. Vasiliki, 99. Kavousi, 100. Mochlos, 101. Aghia Fotia, 102. Chamaizi, 103. Kephala Petras, 104. Praesos, 105. Zou, 106. Livari-Skiadi, 107. Magasa, 108. Itanos, 109. Palaikastro, 110. Petsofas, 111. Pezoules, 112. Zakro, 113. Troy, 114. Hanai Tepe, 115. Iznik, 116. Hagios Aberkios, 117. Yortanli, 118. Babakoy, 119. Sardis, 120. Cevizcioğlu, 121. Ephesus, 122. Muskebi, 123. Bodrum, 124. Datça, 125. Kusura, 126. Hissarlık, 127. Karataş-Semayük, 128. St Nicholas church, 129. Acemhöyük, 130. Yumuk Tepe, 131. Çatalhöyük, 132. Alishar Huyuk, 133. Osmankayasi, 134. Alaca Huyuk, 135. Büyük Gülücek, 136. Amasya Samlar, 137. Kovuklukaya, 138. İkiztepe, 139. Kum-Tepe, 140. Altintepe, 141. Tasmator, 142. Erzurum, 143. Hakmehmet, 144. Tilkitepe, 145. Jebel Mashtale, 146. Tell Masaikh, 147. Tell Ashara, 148. Umm el-Marra, 149. Tell-al-

Judaidah, 150. Ras Shamra, 151. Palmyra, 152. Byblos, 153. Ayios Iakovos-Melia, 154. Enkomi-Ayios Iakovos, 155. Karpasha, 156. Kissonerga-Mosphilia, 157. Kissonerga-Mylouthkia, 158. Lemba Lakkous, 159. Kholetria-Ortos, 160. Souskiou-Vathrykakas, 161. Sotira-Teppes, 162. Agios Savvas, 163. Kalavastos-Tenta, 164. Khirokitia, 165. Peqi'in, 166. Kfar HaHoresh, 167. Megiddo, 168. Dothan, 169. Gezer, 170. Lachish, 171. Jebel Qa'aqir, 172. Tell 'Eitun, 173. Beersheba, 174. Horvat Lassan, 175. Horvat Liqit, 176. Horvat Ma'aravim, 177. Rehovot-in-the-Negev, 178. Wadi Makkok, 179. Jerusalem, 180. Mount Zion, 181. Jericho, 182. Tepe Gawra, 183. Hasanlu, 184. Jarmo, 185. Himrin Basin, 186. Al 'Ubaid, 187. Ur, 188. Jemdet Nasr, 189. Nippur, 190. Ganj Dareh Tepe, 191. Tepe Giyan, 192. Tchoga Zambil, 193. Tepe Sialk, 194. Ghal-e-Kash, 195. Molla Kheil, 196. Tepe Hissar, 197. Tureng Tepe, 198. Shah Tepe, 199. Qua'lat al-Bahrain, 200. Karranah, 201. Abu Saybi, 202. Saar, 203. A'ali Mound 1, 204. Hamad Town, 205. Kish, 206. Al Sufouh, 207. Mowaihat, 208. Tell Abraq, 209. Ed-Dur, 210. Unar, 211. Sh. 602, 212. Sharm, 213. Munayi, 214. Wa'ab, 215. Naslah, 216. Fashgha, 217. Ra's al-Hamra